

Dahshu IDSWG Oncology Working Group Highlights

- Launch of a new taskforce: *Optimizing Clinical Trial Conduct*
- Master protocol ISBS presentation by Cindy Lu
- Submitted public comments to FDA Draft Guidance Documents: *Master Protocols for Drug and Biological Product Development*. <https://www.regulations.gov/comment/FDA-2023-D-5259-0020>
- JSM Session: *Examples and Perspectives Using Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence in Drug Development*
- Multiple manuscripts submitted in adaptive design

Upcoming Conferences

- [The 9th Workshop on Biostatistics and Bioinformatics](#), May 3-5, 2024, Atlanta, Georgia State University, GA
- [The 7th Stat4Onc Annual Symposium](#), May 8-11, 2024, University of Connecticut, Storrs, CT
- [2024 Symposium on Data Science & Statistics](#), June 4-7, 2024, Richmond, Virginia
- [2024 WVAR/IMS/Graybill Annual Meeting](#), June 9-12, 2024, Fort Collins, Colorado
- [ICSA Applied Statistics Symposium](#), June 16-19, 2024, Nashville, Tennessee
- [PSJ](#), June 17-19, 2024, Amsterdam
- [DIA Annual Meeting](#), June 16-20, 2024, San Diego, CA
- [JSM](#), August 3-8, 2024, Portland, Oregon
- [ASA BIOP Regulatory-Industry Statistics Workshop](#), Sept. 25-27, 2024, Rockville, Maryland

Introduction to Real-World Data (RWD) Sources

By Yoko Tanaka†

RWD are data related to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care routinely collected from a variety of sources.

Typical examples of RWD include data derived from electronic health records (EHR), medical claims data, and data from product or disease registries[1].

EHR database contains individual patient record and can provide comprehensive and diverse information from multiple sources within the healthcare system, including medical history, diagnoses, treatment plans, pathology reports, laboratory results, medication records, and provider notes. They usually contain rich information that may not be available from other types of RWD e.g. detailed information on cancer diagnoses, tumor characteristics, treatment plans, and outcomes. Information held within EHRs may be maintained in unstructured text documents and require curation and translation to structured data. However, they do not include comprehensive information on health care provided outside the facility covered by the system such as imaging data.

Claims contain individual patient data recorded for reimbursement purposes including information on diagnoses and services during patient visits from claims for insurance providers. There are open and closed claims type, and open claims data is derived from broad-based healthcare sources and can highlight a patient's activities over a longer timeframe, regardless of a patient's insurance provider. Closed payer claims data is derived from health insurance providers (payers), adjudicated patient's healthcare information during a specific enrollment period. They can provide longitudinal features which enable a clear description of a population over time. They usually contain patient health data across different health care settings, including inpatient visits, outpatient visits, pharmacy etc. They allow analyzing patterns of healthcare utilization, healthcare resource allocation, and associated costs. However, health care services that are not reimbursable by the health plan or program may not be captured.

Registries are designed to collect uniform and systematic clinical data for a specific population of patients with particular disease, including drug exposure, disease, or outcome. Registries also enroll a specific population to collect prespecified patient-level health-related data. They collect unique information not available from other sources, such as detailed and targeted exposure data and patient-reported outcomes using the Case Report Forms (CRFs) which ensure consistent and uniform data collection across different sites or regions. However, some registries may not capture data on care provided outside the system in which the registry is based, similar to the limitations of EHR data.

†Reference

- [1] <https://www.fda.gov/science-research/science-and-research-special-topics/real-world-evidence>
 [2] https://friendsofcancerresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2023-ASCO-Poster-6595_McKelvey.pdf

EHR and claims data can be available from the companies who provide technology and services to harmonize and normalize the data from the various sources or EHR interfaces. For example, seven RWD EHR-focused partners (ConcertAI, COTA, Flatiron Health, Guardian Research Network/IQVIA, Ontada, Syapse, and Tempus) were included in the recent FOCR pilot project presented at American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) Annual Meeting in 2023[2]; and Medical Data Vision[3] in Japan. There are different data products from these companies, some are basic data from the structured sources, some include deeply curated data such as progression and response, and some include additional molecular, biomarker data. Deciding which data product to obtain depends on the research question, availability of the needed data, and budget. Registry data can be available from the registry directly following the registry specific process for request and review[4]. Some RWD, e.g. RWD operated by public institutions, are limited to academic use only or have stringent usage conditions.

Besides relevance of the data source to the research question, other considerations in selecting a RWD source are completeness, comprehensiveness, contemporaneousness and the geographic region of collection. The data product is usually specific to a patient population in a country where the patient medical/claims records are available as in US, Japan, and countries in the European Union (EU). Consideration should be given in the decision of data product which geographic region is of most interest for the purpose of the study.

[3] <https://en.mdv.co.jp/>

[4] https://seer.cancer.gov/data/access_seer_data.pdf